

can be expected from a single seed.

We also cultured another source of explant — young immature panicles (inflorescence) of the cytotsterile stocks — on MS, N₆, and H_e media supplemented with various growth regulators. Callus could be induced after 2 wk of culture from the surface of the spikelets, but the callus appeared to be mostly nonembryogenic.

For practical application of micropropagation techniques to mass production of special breeding stocks, such as cytotsteriles and the elite hybrids, three factors should be

considered: the time required for *in vitro* multiplication, the purity of the genotype in cultured and regenerated plants, and the capacity of regenerants to withstand the transfer from tube to soil. In our experience, within 8-9 wk the multiplication rate of stock as plantlets is 1:200. Rooting for better anchoring capacity and hardening the regenerated plants for transfer from tube to soil may need another 2 wk. Seedlings of transplantable size can be obtained in 11-12 wk.

We examined the regenerated plants for variants induced in callus culture (somaclonal variation). The

regenerants did not exhibit any variation in sterility or other morphological traits. However, our observations were limited to cultured plants obtained directly from embryo calluses without subculturing.

Callus proliferation through several passages of subculture, the level of 2,4-D in the induction medium, and the concentration of BA in the regeneration medium may induce variation in callus cultures. The purity of the genotype maintained in tissue culture multiplication efforts needs critical examination. □

Phenotypic patterns in somaclones from plants regenerated from somatic cell culture of IR lines

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Families of plants regenerated from somatic cell culture of IR36, IR50, IR52, and IR54 were evaluated in the second generation (Sc₂). Four groups were classified by phenotypic patterns and somaclone relationships to donor parents (Table 1): 1) no segregation within the family, similar to parent

type (SPT) (82.9%); 2) no segregation (uniform) within the family but dissimilar to parent type (DPT) (1.7%); 3) limited segregation involving one or two characters (simple segregation); and 4) more than two characters segregating simultaneously.

We found no significant differences in character between the SPTs and donor variety, but DPTs and the donor variety significantly differed in days from sowing to flowering, plant type, shape and color of leaves, length of flag leaf, plant height, effective tillers, length of panicles, seed numbers/panicle, and seed shape (Table 2). However, each DPT population was still uniform within the family. The coefficient of variation of all characters was less in the DPTs than in the donor variety, showing that the DPTs were homozygous. □

Table 1. Phenotypic patterns of the Sc₂ generation in somaclones of indica rice. ^a Guangzhou, China.

Sc ₂ lines derived from	Sc ₂ (no.) in given phenotypic pattern				Total (no.)
	No segregation		With segregation		
	Similar to donor parent	Dissimilar to donor parent	Simple segregation	Complex segregation	
IR36	99 (77.9)	5 (3.9)	7 (5.5)	16 (12.6)	127
IR50	2 (50.0)	0	1 (25)	1 (25)	4
IR52	2 (25.0)	0	0	6 (75.0)	8
IR54 ^b	136 (90.6)	0	11 (7.4)	3 (2.0)	150
Total	239 (82.9)	5 (4.7)	19 (6.3)	26 (9.1)	289

^a Values in parentheses are percentages. ^b Maturity of IR54 too late to evaluate characters, classified according to days from seeding to flowering.

Table 2. Agronomic characteristics of nonsegregating somaclones and donor variety. ^a Guangzhou, China.

Variety and somaclones ^b	Seeding to harvest (d)	Blade color ^c	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Effective panicles (no.)	Seeds/panicle (no.)	Seed setting (%)
IR36	118	L	71.1 ± 3.7	19.5 ± 2.4	18.0 ± 4.2	98.7 ± 22.1	81.6 ± 10.3
SPT	S1	L	68.4 ± 2.0	20.5 ± 2.1	14.1 ± 2.0*	128.1 ± 21.4**	80.3 ± 8.8
	S2	L	71.4 ± 3.2	20.9 ± 2.4*	15.1 ± 3.0*	116.8 ± 12.5**	82.4 ± 5.7
	S3	L	72.6 ± 4.2	19.6 ± 1.1	10.1 ± 2.7**	96.5 ± 15.8	79.9 ± 14.5
	S4	L	70.8 ± 4.6	22.6 ± 2.3*	15.7 ± 3.5	87.6 ± 4.8*	71.9 ± 8.8**
DPT	D1	D	59.4 ± 3.7**	20.4 ± 1.1	15.6 ± 3.2	78.5 ± 6.3***	86.4 ± 6.3*
	D2	D	52.8 ± 2.9**	16.1 ± 1.4**	15.1 ± 3.0*	68.8 ± 8.1**	78.8 ± 8.9
	D3	D	61.9 ± 3.7**	18.7 ± 2.5	11.0 ± 2.9**	76.9 ± 5.7**	83.1 ± 8.0
	D4	D	58.8 ± 3.1**	16.9 ± 1.7**	14.2 ± 2.9*	55.9 ± 6.4**	74.3 ± 10.8*
	D5	D	59.9 ± 2.0**	17.8 ± 1.4**	10.6 ± 3.7**	66.8 ± 5.5**	83.8 ± 7.9

^a *Significantly different from the donor parent variety at 0.05 level. **Significantly different from the donor parent variety at 0.01 level. ^b SPT = similar to donor parent variety, DPT = dissimilar to donor parent variety. ^c L = light color, D = dark color.